

Protocol for an Observational Study of the Effects of High School Football on Cognition Late in Life Using a New Matching Method: Revised*

Katherine Brumberg[†], Dylan S. Small, and Paul R. Rosenbaum
Department of Statistics and Data Science, University of Pennsylvania

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Abstract

Background: A study in JAMA Neurology of the effect of high school football exposure on cognition at age 72 did not detect a significant effect. Using newly available data at the later age of 81, we look for such an effect at an age when cognitive decline is substantially more common.

Methods and Analysis: We propose a longitudinal observational study with 1155 high school graduates after exclusion criteria. 426 of these graduates played football in high school and 729 did not. The primary outcome is a combination of two measures collected in the 2020 wave of the Wisconsin Longitudinal Study (WLS). One component is a recently developed measure of cognitive functioning, the “Telephone Interview for Cognitive Status-modified” (TICS_m) score. The second component is a consensus diagnosis made after a longer interview of participants who performed poorly in terms of the TICS_m score.

A new matching method is created in order to construct triples of either one football player and two controls or two football players and one control such that the measured covariates are balanced within triples of each type. Such a design has greater design sensitivity

*This protocol has been revised after starting the final analysis in small ways. A list of changes between the original and current version is in Section 8.

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than one which also allows matched pairs. We will use the “aberrant rank statistic” to evaluate cognitive scores outside the normal range. Additionally, we will conduct a secondary analysis on the TICSm score alone. The sensitivity of these analyses to unmeasured biases will be assessed. Finally, we will consider two unaffected outcomes, periodontitis and cancer, in an effort to detect unmeasured biases.

Discussion: This study, to the best of our knowledge, is the first prospective longitudinal study to look at the effects of high school football at such a late age of 81.

Keywords: Causal inference; design sensitivity; full matching; propensity score; subset matching; triples design; pre-analysis plan

1 Background and Motivation for Study

In 2017, Deshpande et al. studied the impact of high school football on cognitive outcomes measured at 65 and 72 years of age in the Wisconsin Longitudinal Study (WLS), a cohort study of one third of high school graduates in Wisconsin in 1957. The primary outcome was a composite cognition measure combining the scores from the letter fluency and delayed word recall tests at 72 years of age. Comparing football players and matched controls, Deshpande et al. (2017) did not find a statistically or clinically significant harmful association between playing football in high school and cognition.

Although dementia does sometimes occur by ages 65 and 72, it becomes much more common at older ages. In 2023, the WLS released data from a new wave of interviews conducted starting in 2020 entitled ILIAD 2020 (Initial Lifetime’s Impact on Alzheimer’s Disease and Related Dementias). Someone who was 18 at high school graduation in 1957 would have been 81 in 2020. These new data include an improved measure of cognitive decline, “The Telephone Interview for Cognitive Status-modified” (TICSm), a 10 minute validated screening assessment for dementia risk collected during a short interview (see Knopman et al. (2010)). Additionally, the participants who performed the worst on the screening assessment were invited to participate in a longer interview with a trained survey interviewer and an Advanced Practice Provider. The longer interview provided data that was presented to clinicians at a consensus conference, at which point the clinicians determined the level of impairment of each participant.

To address the new question of whether high school football affects dementia risk at around 81 years of age, we use the recently released TICSm score and the consensus diagnoses as our cognitive outcomes. This new wave of WLS data provides improved measurements of cognition at a more advanced age when dementia is more common.

2 Eligibility and Exclusion Criteria

We closely followed the protocol in Deshpande et al. (2016) in establishing our eligibility and exclusion criteria.

The WLS has 10,317 subjects in total. As there were very few women playing high school football in the mid-1950's, we only consider the 4,991 men in the WLS. Participation in football was based on extraction of data from high school yearbooks. We exclude 457 men who did not have a yearbook, 114 men whose yearbooks did not include activity information for any of the students, and 50 men who did not appear in their yearbooks. We also exclude an additional 397 men whose activity participation was imputed by WLS by looking at group photographs. This leaves us with 3,973 men with adequate yearbook activity information.

2,627 of these men did not play football. Of these, we exclude 65 men who played a different collision sport that could cause mild traumatic brain injuries (soccer, hockey, lacrosse, or wrestling). We thus have a total of 3,908 eligible men: 1,346 who played football in high school and 2,562 who did not.

3 Study Outcomes

Our primary outcome combines information from the short and long interviews that composed the 2020 wave of the WLS, when the graduates were between 79 and 83 years old. The interviews for this wave started in 2019 and were completed by 2022. The two components are described in Sections 3.1 and 3.2; the composite outcome is defined in Section 6.1.

3.1 Adjusted TICSm Score

2,752 of the 3,908 eligible men do not have data from the short interview. Of these men, 2,247 were not surveyed in this wave, 95 refused, 76 were not found, 255 were deceased, 23 were away or unavailable, and 56 were unable. We thus have 1,156 men remaining in our sample who have primary outcome information available. One additional individual, a football player, is also dropped due to missing the unaffected outcomes (see section 4), leaving a final sample of 1,155 men, 426 of whom played football and 729 of whom did not.

The “Telephone Interview for Cognitive Status-modified” (TICSm) as used in the WLS is scored out of 50 points (WLS 2022). There are separate scores for orientation to name (2 points), phone number (1 point), age (1 point), immediate recall (10 points), orientation to time (5 points), backwards count (2 points), naming (4 points), serial 7 subtractions (5 points), repetition (2 points), recent memory (4 points), praxis (2 points), opposites (2

points), and delayed recall (10 points). All participants with TICSm scores have each of these component scores available.

The WLS made two adjustments to this score. First, they subtracted one point from the TICSm score for the 10 percent of the original sample that showed the largest cognitive decline between 2004 and 2011 based on a combined measure from 4 components: immediate and delayed recall, letter fluency and digit ordering. Second, they subtracted two points from the score for anyone with more than a high school education. The WLS used these adjusted scores to determine whether additional data would be collected, so the WLS data are shaped by these adjustments. For this reason, we used the adjusted scores as provided by WLS. Henceforth, when we refer to TICSm scores, we mean the score provided by WLS incorporating these adjustments.

3.2 Dementia diagnosis

Individuals with an adjusted TICSm score below 29 were invited for a longer interview with a trained survey interviewer and an Advanced Practice Provider that resulted in a consensus diagnosis for dementia.

As is always true of a permutation test of the null hypothesis of no effect (Lehmann & Romano 2005, Theorem 5.8.1), our analyses condition on the marginal distribution of the outcome; so, we can look at this marginal distribution during the study design without disrupting the significance levels of our tests, provided that we do not examine the treatment assignments.

Looking at the marginal distribution of TICSm scores in Figure 1, we see there are 365 individuals with scores below 29. The WLS invited these people for the longer interview. 320 completed the interview, 22 refused or were unable to be contacted, 17 died before completing the interview, and 6 were physically or mentally unable. For 1 person who completed the long interview, the consensus panel did not come to a diagnosis.

For those who died or were too ill to be interviewed, a proxy was invited to fill out the Dementia Questionnaire (DQ) as an informant. This questionnaire was scored for dementia and an algorithm was used to make a diagnosis. A clinician then looked at all the data available and confirmed the diagnosis. Of the 17 people who died before the long interview, 8 had DQs filled out by proxies. Of the 6 people unable to participate in the long interview, 4 had DQs filled out. An additional 2 people participated in the long interview and also had a proxy fill out the DQ.

The results from the long interviews and the DQs were combined by the WLS to create a “positive predicted value summary score”, which classifies the participants as having normal

cognition, mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or dementia. We refer to this outcome as the diagnosis. Distinction was also made between patients presumed to have Alzheimer’s Disease or not, but we do not plan to use this distinctions in our analyses due to the size of the sample.

We can see the relationship between the adjusted TICSm score and the diagnosis in Figure 2. Of the 365 participants with adjusted TICSm scores below 29, 142 had normal cognition, 145 had MCI, 44 had dementia, and 34 do not have conclusive results from the long interview or DQ.

Additionally, 2 people were mistakenly invited to participate in the long interview who were ineligible. These two individuals had TICSm scores of 29 and 31 and diagnoses of normal and MCI, respectively. Another 6 people had DQs filled out even though they had higher scores. One of these 6 was classified as having dementia and had a TICSm score of 29. The others were all classified as normal and had scores of 29, 30, 32, 37, and 38. Since we should not have this data on these individuals, we disregard the diagnoses of these 8 participants and use only their TICSm scores.

Figure 1: The marginal distribution of the adjusted TICSm score. The vertical line is at 29. The WLS invited individuals with scores < 29 for further interviews.

Figure 2: The marginal distribution of the adjusted TICSm score, grouped by diagnosis. Of the 365 participants with adjusted TICSm scores below 29 eligible for further interviews, 142 had normal cognition, 145 had MCI, 44 had dementia, and 34 did not have conclusive results from the long interview or DQ.

4 Unaffected outcomes

We plan to consider two unaffected outcomes in our sensitivity analyses (Rosenbaum 1989, 2023). Both are from the 2020 wave, meaning the same people who have TICSm scores were asked these questions around age 81:

1. Has a doctor ever told Participant they have periodontal or gum disease?
2. Has a doctor ever told Participant they have cancer or a malignant tumor, not including minor skin cancers?

Our presumption is that playing football in high school causes neither periodontal disease nor cancers (except perhaps skin cancer). This presumption may be in error, but it seems far more plausible than an assumption of no unmeasured confounders; so, a plausible presumption may usefully test a doubtful assumption.

Participants could respond to these questions by saying that they did not know or refuse to answer. One person refused the questions on both periodontitis and cancer and was dropped from the analysis, leaving 1,155 people as the final sample. For periodontitis, five people answered they did not know, and due to the wording of the question, we have placed them in the “no” category. The prevalence of periodontitis in the sample, without looking at treatment assignment, is 114/1,155 and the prevalence of cancer in the sample is 348/1,155.

5 Matching

5.1 Covariates

Covariates we consider are listed in Table 1. These include all covariates from Deshpande et al. (2017) with the exception of high school size and APOE4 variant. High school size is excluded since it may be considered a prod-to-treatment that influences whether a high school has a football team, but does not otherwise influence cognitive decline later in life (Pimentel et al. 2016). APOE4 variant is not included since it is only available for a subset of participants and Deshpande et al. (2017) did not find it to significantly modify the association of high school football with cognition at ages 65 and 72. We include four extra covariates that are also included in Gaulton et al. (2020): family history of early stroke, family history of Alzheimer’s, childhood asthma, and childhood polio.

The frequency of missing data for each covariate is also listed in Table 1. Missing-data indicators are added to the propensity score model for covariates with at least 35 missing values out of the 1,155 people in the sample, as described in Rosenbaum & Rubin (1984, Appendix). This coding is intended to balance the visible pattern of missing data; whereas, confounding due to the unknown, unmeasured values of covariates is an aspect of unmeasured confounding. Two exceptions are for “parent support for college” and “family history of Alzheimer’s”, whose missing-data indicators are perfectly colinear with other covariates.

Covariate	Missing values
Duncan socioeconomic index of aspired job	363
High school rank	63
Parental income	38
Father education level	21
Mother education level	6
Duncan socioeconomic index of father's job	7
Planned future education	85
IQ	0
Outstanding student	0
Participated in musical ensemble	0
Participated in debate	0
Participated in school govt	0
Participated in school pubs	0
Rural: father was a farmer	0
Planned to serve in military	0
Catholic high school	0
Lived with both parents	0
Mother working	4
Teachers encouraged college	55
Parents encouraged college	35
Friends planned on college	129
Discussed plans with teachers	23
Discussed plans with parents	13
Family wealth	28
Parent support for college	124
Family history of early stroke	122
Family history of Alzheimer's	122
Childhood asthma	159
Childhood polio	156

Table 1: Amount of missingness for each covariate. Missingness indicators were created for the bolded covariates with at least 35 missing values out of 1,155 that were not colinear with other included covariates.

All covariates, as well as indicators for missing covariate values, are included in the logit model used to estimate the propensity score. We then stratify on the quartiles of the estimated propensity score and on whether or not the person participated in school government in high school. Participation in high school government is used to define strata

because it is particularly difficult to balance. In total, we have eight strata, as shown in Table 2.

A covariate distance matrix is created using the Mahalanobis distance combining the estimated propensity score (both in its original form and discretized into eight equally sized categories), high school rank, IQ test score, father’s and mother’s years of education, and the socioeconomic status of the father’s occupation discretized into three equally sized categories. Ultimately, we want the match to control for the eight strata while making the covariate distance as small as possible.

5.2 Triples match

We match treated and control units in sets of three, such that each match is a triple with either one treated and two control units or vice versa. To do this, we construct a new algorithm which will be described in the main manuscript.

The number of treated and control individuals matched are in the bottom half of Table 2. The number of triples of each type are in Table 3.

The covariate balance attained by this match can be seen in Figures 3 and 4 and Table 4.

Table 2: Counts for each stratum, which is defined by the propensity score quartile (Q1-Q4) and participation in school government (–G and +G). For the sole purpose of a display that complies with WLS rules on confidentiality, the strata for the first two quartiles have been collapsed across school government to avoid reporting small cell counts.

Stratum	Q1	Q2	Q3–G	Q3+G	Q4–G	Q4+G	Total
Football Before Matching	48	88	84	22	42	142	426
Control Before Matching	241	201	158	24	24	81	729
Total			242	46	66	223	1155
Quartile Total	289	289	288		289		1155
Matched Football Players	48	88	84	22	42	142	426
Matched Controls	96	173	156	23	24	80	552
Matched Total	144	261	240	45	66	222	978

Table 3: Counts of 1-to-2 and 2-to-1 matched sets in the triples design.

Stratum	Q1	Q2	Q3-G	Q3+G	Q4-G	Q4+G	Total
1 - 2 Matched Triples	48	86	76	8	2	6	226
2 - 1 Matched Triples	0	1	4	7	20	68	100
Stratum in the Algorithm	1	2, 3	4	5	6	7	
Treated to use = m_{tk}^*	48	88	84	22	42	142	426
2 - 1 triples = b_k	0	1	4	7	20	68	100
Supply = $m_{tk}^* - b_k$	48	87	80	15	22	74	326

Figure 3: Propensity scores for a triples match built from 426 football players and 729 controls, 1155 = 426 + 729. The match has $M = 226 + 100 = 326$ triples. It includes all 426 = 226 + 2 × 100 football players and 552 = 226 × 2 + 100 of 729 controls.

Figure 4: Boxplots of treated-minus-control pair differences for six covariates included in the Mahalanobis distance, namely the propensity score, high school class rank, father’s and mother’s years of education, IQ, and father’s occupational status. “B” are the $426 \times 729 = 310554$ differences before matching, ‘1’ are the differences in blocks with one treated individual, ‘2’ are the differences in the blocks with two treated individuals, and ‘W’ is the weighted combination that duplicates the differences for the blocks with two treated individuals.

Table 4: Covariate balance before and after matching and weighting. The treated mean is T , the mean in the control group is Cb before matching and weighting and Cmw after matching and weighting, the pooled standard deviation before matching is s , and the standardized differences are $Db = (T - Cb)/s$ and $Dmw = (T - Cmw)/s$. Rows are sorted by $|Db|$. **Bold** text indicates a covariate explicitly used in matching. Standardized differences above 0.20 are bolded as well.

	T	Cb	Cmw	Db	Dmw
Propensity Score	0.46	0.32	0.44	0.82	0.11
PS-Strata	3.00	2.21	3.00	0.75	-0.00
Participated in school govt	0.39	0.15	0.39	0.55	0.00
Teachers encouraged college	0.62	0.47	0.58	0.30	0.07
Participated in debate	0.31	0.21	0.30	0.24	0.02
Mother education level	11.10	10.46	10.92	0.23	0.07
Planned future education	2.54	2.05	2.51	0.22	0.01
High school rank- missing	0.03	0.07	0.03	-0.21	-0.03
Participated in school pubs	0.25	0.17	0.24	0.20	0.03
Participated in musical ensemble	0.36	0.27	0.34	0.19	0.04
Parent support for college: cannot	0.23	0.31	0.25	-0.18	-0.04
Parents encouraged college	0.70	0.62	0.69	0.18	0.03
Family wealth: Considerably above	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.17	0.11
Catholic high school	0.08	0.13	0.08	-0.17	-0.01
High school rank	52.25	47.79	53.14	0.16	-0.03
Parent support for college: can with sacrifice	0.62	0.54	0.60	0.15	0.03
Discussed plans with parents: Sometimes	0.40	0.47	0.41	-0.14	-0.02
Parental income	74.20	64.29	71.34	0.13	0.04
Lived with both parents	0.93	0.89	0.93	0.12	-0.01
Discussed plans with parents: Very much	0.58	0.52	0.56	0.12	0.03
Friends planned on college	0.47	0.41	0.48	0.11	-0.02
Discussed plans with teachers: Not at all	0.23	0.28	0.25	-0.11	-0.03
Duncan socioeconomic index of aspired job	607.47	580.01	598.40	0.10	0.03
Father education level	10.28	9.93	10.05	0.10	0.06
Childhood asthma- missing	0.12	0.15	0.12	-0.08	-0.00
Childhood polio- missing	0.12	0.15	0.12	-0.08	-0.01
Discussed plans with teachers: Very much	0.11	0.09	0.11	0.08	0.01
Duncan socioeconomic index of father's job	332.32	313.94	313.52	0.08	0.08
Family history of early stroke- missing	0.09	0.11	0.09	-0.07	-0.00
Family wealth: Average	0.66	0.69	0.69	-0.07	-0.05
Mother working	0.38	0.35	0.37	0.06	0.03
Teachers encouraged college- missing	0.04	0.05	0.04	-0.06	-0.00
Discussed plans with parents: Not at all	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.06	-0.03
Discussed plans with teachers: Sometimes	0.66	0.63	0.65	0.05	0.02
Planned future education- missing	0.07	0.08	0.08	-0.05	-0.05
Parents encouraged college- missing	0.03	0.03	0.02	-0.04	0.05
Planned to serve in military	0.25	0.26	0.22	-0.03	0.07
IQ	104.05	103.71	104.33	0.02	-0.02
Childhood asthma	0.05	0.05	0.05	-0.02	-0.02
Parental income- missing	0.03	0.03	0.03	-0.02	-0.01
Rural: father was a farmer	0.18	0.19	0.19	-0.02	-0.04
Family wealth: Somewhat below	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.02	-0.02
Family history of early stroke	0.11	0.11	0.11	-0.02	-0.00
Family history of Alzheimer's	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.02	-0.00
Parent support for college: can easily	0.15	0.14	0.15	0.01	-0.00
Outstanding student	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.01	-0.07
Family wealth: Considerably below	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.04
Friends planned on college- missing	0.11	0.11	0.12	-0.01	-0.02
Childhood polio	0.02	0.02	0.02	-0.00	-0.02
Family wealth: Somewhat above	0.22	0.22	0.21	-0.00	0.02
Duncan socioeconomic index of aspired job- missing	0.31	0.31	0.29	0.00	0.04

6 Plan for the Primary Analysis

6.1 Cognitive Decline as an Aberrant Response Outside the Normal Range

Many outcomes exhibit a combination of normal and aberrant variation, or variation outside the normal range. For example, there is a wide normal range of birth weights that are without discernible health consequences, but there are also birth weights below that range that place the newborn at risk. Aberrant ranks ignore variation in the normal range and focus on variation in the range of clinical significance (Rosenbaum & Silber 2008).

Since we are interested in the relationship between high school football and dementia, we care about cognitive scores below the normal range. We are not interested in treatment effects among those that have normal cognition with or without treatment. Perhaps being a star football player gets you a college scholarship, and perhaps college affects cognition in some way, but this normal variation in cognition is not of interest when studying dementia. This analysis thus lends itself to methods used for investigating aberrant effects. In particular, we intend to use the aberrant rank test (Rosenbaum & Silber 2008, Heng et al. 2021).

We first define aberrant as having an adjusted TICSm score below 29. In the aberrant ranks, anyone with a TICSm score of 29 or higher is assigned a value of 0, signifying that they do not have an aberrant response, and the remaining TICSm scores, for matched individuals only, are ranked. The more severe the evidence of cognitive decline, the higher the rank.

To combine the two components of the primary outcome for the aberrant responses, we use a version of coherent scores (Rosenbaum 1994). To form these scores for matched individuals, we start by comparing any two participants, scoring a pair as a 1, 0, or -1 for that comparison. To score a 1, all outcomes available for the focal participant must be no less severe than those of the other participant, and at least one outcome must be more severe. To score a -1, all outcomes available for the focal participant must be no more severe than those of the other participant, and at least one outcome must be less severe. All other comparisons are assigned a value of 0. To construct the coherent score for the focal participant, we sum the scores that compare the focal participant to someone else (Mantel 1981, Rosenbaum 1994). Finally, we create coherent ranks by shifting all coherent scores by a positive constant such that the smallest coherent rank is equal to 1. The individuals showing the most evidence of cognitive decline have the greatest coherent ranks.

In Figures 5 and 6, we see how the coherent ranks correspond to the two components of the primary outcome. Comparing Figure 5 to Figure 2, we see that the coherent ranks accentuate the differences between the groups diagnosed as having normal cognition, MCI,

and dementia. Comparing the coherent ranks to the adjusted TICS_m scores in Figure 6, we see that the coherent ranks follow the TICS_m scores within the diagnoses while still incorporating the extra information we have about these diagnoses for the aberrant responses. The two scores have correlation -0.81.

Figure 5: The marginal distribution of the coherent ranks for the aberrant individuals that are included in the match, grouped by diagnosis. The coherent rank combines the TICS_m score and the diagnosis into a single number. When the TICS_m score and diagnosis disagree, the coherent rank is pulled toward the middle; so, the largest and smallest ranks reflect agreement or coherence between the TICS_m score and the diagnosis.

Figure 6: The marginal distribution of the coherent ranks on the y-axis and the adjusted TICSm scores on the x-axis for the aberrant individuals that are included in the match. The points are colored by diagnosis and the size corresponds to the number of observations at that position. The coherent rank combines the TICSm score and the diagnosis into a single number.

6.2 Test for harmful effect overall

Critics of high school football argue that it may cause or worsen dementia. We thus have a one-sided test where the null hypothesis is no effect and the alternative hypothesis is that there is a harmful effect of playing high school football on cognitive outcomes. We test this using the `sentrip` function in the `triplesmatch` package on the coherent ranks, constructed as described in §6.1. Nonaberrant responses have a rank of 0. The `sentrip` function takes these scores and performs a within-triple permutation test using the test statistic $\sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^3 Z_{ij} q_{ij}$ where Z_{ij} is the treatment indicator for person j in match i and q_{ij} is the coherent rank. This function is only very slightly modified from the `senfm` function in the `sensitivityfull` package in order to allow for arbitrary scores such as the coherent ranks as opposed to Huber’s M-statistics (Rosenbaum 2007).

6.3 One-sided confidence interval for effect on TICSm scores alone

Of course, we are also interested in the size of any potential harmful effect. Perhaps high school football has harmful effects, but perhaps these effects are nonzero but small. We thus perform a secondary analysis on the TICSm scores alone and test for near-equivalence.

We measure the effect size by β , which is the shift in adjusted TICSm scores due to playing football in high school. We seek a one-sided confidence interval of the form $[\beta_0, 0]$ or $[\beta_0, 0)$, where $[\beta_0, 0]$ includes 0 and $[\beta_0, 0)$ excludes 0. The form $[\beta_0, 0)$ says that there is a harmful effect, while $[\beta_0, 0]$ says there may be no harmful effect. Values of β_0 far from 0 imply that the harm may be substantial, while values close to 0 imply that the harm is small, if it exists. For discussion of confidence intervals and hypothesis tests that change the direction of the test as the hypothesized parameter value changes, see Bauer & Kieser (1996), Goeman et al. (2010) and Rosenbaum (2021, pp. 121-122).

To test for evidence of harm, we test the hypothesis of “no shift”, $H_0 : \beta = 0$, against the alternative $H_A : \beta < 0$. To determine a limit on the quantity of harm, we test the hypothesis of a shift of $H_0 : \beta = \beta_0$, with $\beta_0 < 0$, against the alternative $H_0 : \beta > \beta_0$. Doing this for all $\beta_0 < 0$ results in a confidence interval having one of two forms, $[\beta_0, 0]$ or $[\beta_0, 0)$. For any given β_0 , we subtract β_0 from the treated responses and perform a one-sided permutation test using the within-block means of TICSm as a test statistic. The set of β_0 ’s not rejected at level α is the confidence interval. At integer values of β_0 , we also consider the permutation test using the aberrant ranks of the TICSm scores. Because the TICSm scores are heavily tied, we cannot use any form of ranks when testing noninteger values.

7 Sensitivity Analyses

If we reject the null of no harm in the primary analysis, then we can also find the smallest amount of bias (measured by the parameter Γ) that would alter this result (Rosenbaum 2018). This is done by altering the `Gamma` parameter in the `sentrip` function.

In addition to the confidence interval calculated for harm on adjusted TICSm scores, we will calculate such intervals at multiple different Γ values, representing different amounts of potential bias from unmeasured confounding.

Since we do not expect playing high school football to affect the occurrence of periodontitis or cancer, we can also conduct hypothesis tests for the effect of football on these binary health outcomes. If we observe a difference, we strongly suspect it reflects some unmeasured bias (see for example Rosenbaum (1989), Weiss (2002), Tchetgen Tchetgen (2014) among others). We can find the Γ s at which these analyses stop rejecting the null effect, and we

will know that the bias in the study must be at least this large. These analyses use the Mantel-Haenszel test. We conduct the two-sided tests for periodontitis and cancer each at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level. We do not correct for multiple testing, since we prefer to find bias when there is none (increased type I error) rather than miss potential biases in the study.

If rejection of the null hypothesis of no effect occurs at $\Gamma > 1$, we will also use an informed sensitivity analysis as in Rosenbaum (2023). This may actually increase the Γ at which the main analysis is sensitive, since the same pattern of bias must explain both the effects of the unaffected outcomes as well as the primary outcome. This is done using the `informedsentrip` function in the `triples` package, which is a very slightly adapted version of the `informedsen` function in the `informedSen` package that allows for having two treated units in a triple and for conducting a one-sided primary hypothesis test.

8 Amendments to the Protocol Made After Analysis Began

The original protocol was completed before the analysis began. After the analysis began, we made the following changes that are reflected in this revised protocol.

Before the analysis began, we had not fully digested a basic fact about the Wisconsin Longitudinal Study’s decision to attempt to collect clinical data only if TICS_m was < 29 . As the tail of a discrete random variable, the TICS_m that are < 29 exhibit many ties at 28, quite a few ties at 27, and so on, for scores near the normal range of TICS_m. This is visible in Figure 1 of the protocol. For instance, the many people with both a TICS_m of 28 and a clinical diagnosis of “Normal” have minimal evidence of cognitive decline. Using average ranks for ties tends to give these people ranks much larger than minimal, precisely because there are many ties at 28.

In this revised protocol, we made two adjustments to the analysis related to the ties. First, we computed the coherent ranks from matched people with TICS_m < 29 , then added a constant to make the smallest coherent score into a 1, giving a 0 to everyone with a TICS_m ≥ 29 . This avoids a large gap between TICS_m = 29 and (TICS_m = 28, Normal Diagnosis). Second, for confidence intervals for the TICS_m, we used the mean of all TICS_m rather than the aberrant rank statistics.

Finally, we corrected an error in labeling Figure 3.

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